

Design thinking and artisanship to saddle competition and consumer behaviour change; A case study of Vogue Jewellers, Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

Purpose

The research articulates one of the premium jewellery makers: Vogue Jewellers. Their future and existing market strategies that have been analysed. This research works with the themes on design thinking, product innovations and consumer behaviour. In this study, a comprehensive literature review is presented both from Western and Eastern perspective. The literature based research insights provide for a detailed perspective on the aspects of Design, Marketing, product value benefit and the historical development and use of jewellery. Vogue as an organisation, has been at the forefront of innovation in jewellery and marketing accuracy that has appealed to the masses. Some of the Television advertisements are still recalled by the masses, even though they might not have personally visited one of the branches.

Design/methodology/approach

An in depth design approach is used where the role of the research involves in-depth interviewing of the founders - Vogue Jewellery. Qualitative research methodology has been used to analyse and interpret the findings gathered. The family members involved in the management and administration were interviewed.

Findings

The paper highlights the history of the Vogue Jewellers, the marketing strategies and successful campaign strategy. It is understandable the themes of strong branding on quality, craftsmanship, product designs that are unique. Vogue has been able to be at the forefront of innovation.

Originality/value

Gold jewellers have been present historically in Sri Lanka, but there is little research on the marketing aspect of the businesses involved. The current research provides practical insights into a business blueprint of a successful luxury jeweller in Sri Lanka.

Key words: *Design thinking, Innovation, Jewellery production, Marketing, Product design, Vogue Jewellery*

1.INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to research

This research evaluates how a manufacturer and artisan of gold jewellery can outperform the market conditions, negative consumer sentiments towards gold jewellery, and the success with marketing that has been achieved. In Sri Lanka, the gold jewellery makers are identifiable from a variety of backgrounds and the number of sales and selling outlets are in excess of 25,000 as per Google Maps (2024). The vast majority of these gold jewellers fall into unbranded jewellery market category - often facilitating purchase at the rural levels. .

It is an oligopoly market of premium jewellers. Jewellers who have built trust for their brand. Invested in marketing, branding, and dedicated their efforts to innovation. A total list of six (6) such brands could be identified. The list of premium jewellery branded providers are listed out in table 1. The listing is not done on order of sales, revenue or rating.

Table 1: List of branded gold jewellery manufacturers

1	Vogue jewellery
2	Raja Jewellery
3	Mallika Hemachandra Jewellery
4	Bullion Exchange Jewellery.
5	Devi Jewellers
6	Wellawatta Nithyakalyani Jewellery

1.2 Background to Vogue

Vogue Jewellers is a family business that started their operations down south of Sri Lanka. The business expanded its operations to Colombo in 1962. In Colombo, the operations were placed 74, 1st Cross Street, Pettah. Since then the business has been able to work out better quality and craftsmanship to enable further.

1.3 Research questions

The research involved understanding the following:

- [1] How does an organisation face the shift in consumer behaviour?
- [2] What are the potential barriers impacting growth of crafted jewellery reaching the international market place?
- [3] How did the business align its marketing strategies to convince the value benefit?

1.4 Research objectives

Following research objectives are established.

[1] To gain an understanding of consumer behaviour in the jewellery sector

[2] To understand the shifts in consumer behaviour in the branded premium jewellery industry.

[3] To understand the enablers of marketing communication in the branded premium jewellery industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several literature are observable in the theoretical themes of product design, branding and marketing of jewellery. However, a literature gap persists in the aspect of branded jewellery in the Sri Lankan market space. In comparison to that of India; the number of research output on the jewellery market in Sri Lanka has been extremely limited.

2.1 Jewellery marketing

Bliss (2016) has presented a detailed understanding of Jewellery Wearing in the 1920s. Discussion is carried out outlining the aspect of the value of jewellery, how it is represented and “performed”. The evaluation of 1928 work of Bliss (2016) identifies several aspects of the Jewellery marketing dimensions related with fashion. Fashion aspects are discussed in the angle of complementing jewellery to the attire - occasion. It is interesting to see the transformation of jewellery to meet the requirements. Jewellery could be traced to see in the modernisation state as a symbol of femininity and trust.

On the other hand in the Asian context, the role of jewellery could be articulated as a method of storing wealth. India is one of the largest countries with the storage of gold at household levels. (Daniel, 2019)

The artisanship is set out with learning from childhood, where communities are dedicated in India, where the jewellery making skills are learnt from childhood. The sellers for jewellery were businessmen who focused on marketing and selling rather than manufacturing. In the post 1990s, the role of gold jewellery making has seen increased intervention of jewellery making machines. Craftsmen are nevertheless useful and are integral in the system of manufacturing gold, where a higher amount could be sought for the “man hours” involved. A stark contrast between jewellery purchase attitudes are seen. In the aspect of western literature - Serdari and Levy (2020) it could be identified that the jewellery making does have only an ornamental value, while the Asian perspective Jewellery is set out both as a benefit of storing wealth and design to wear for cultural, social events. Pereira *et al* (2019) has included a comprehensive analysis with the case study methodology on the “Larry Jewellery”. The authors justify the importance of looking at the business model and specifically marketing make up of the jewellery industry.

Alot of variety in jewellery marketing and categorisation could be found. Firstly the function of “name plate jewellery”, has been presented. It is where a user inserts the name into the different artefact types: necklaces, earrings, rings, belt buckles, or bracelets. It's customary

to provide name plate jewellery for newborn babies or as gifts. Further the western literature has been able to glorify the growth of Rap trends, which have emphasised on the aspect of enabling name plate jewellery more.

Figure 1: Name plate jewellery
Source: Serdari and Levy (2020)

Each country has specialised in their product configuration and marketing of their gold jewellery. Dubai's Gold Souk (2024) is famous for providing jewellery that is unique in colour, variety and pricing. Similarly, Sri Lankan artisanship is valued globally.

2.2 Technological intervention in the jewellery market place

Cordeiro (2003) has identified that there is a need for jewellery stores to go online and capture the opportunities that are set out with e-commerce. The work of Cordeiro (2003) cites a case study of how a retail organisation moved into an e-commerce platform. Today's businesses are exposed to automation, IT involvement in Customer relationship management and also the input of smart technologies that could provide "customer value".

2.3 Sri Lankan Jewellery market place

New York, Geneva, India, Hong Kong could be identified as key cities that drive Gold jewellery markets. The ability of these markets to run high value auctions. The quality and speciality of each country drives foreign investment and income. However, Sri Lanka also has a historical gem and jewellery trade that could be traced back to 1000 years back. The commercial success however has been limited to compete with global markets, due to the lack of international focus by the large players. The traders in gem and jewellery have focused less on value addition. The work of Pereira *et al* (2019) highlights the ability of

jewellery stores to appeal to foreigners. Travellers are willing to spend money on valuables, often accounting for 14% of the Hong Kong visitors from mainland China.

The National Gem and Jewellery Authority (NGJA) acts as a promoter of the industry. Free market conditions are set out, with NGJA acting as a facilitator and promoter.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a case study based method, as the research focuses on only one (1) organisation in the premium jewellery market. The population of premium jewellery makers in Sri Lanka are indicated on the Sri Lanka Export Development board website (2023) as forty nine (49). It is similar to an oligopoly market with the branded stores. The trust in purity of gold, craftsmanship and certificates of authenticity lead to positive customer preferences. As such, the role of selecting Vogue Jewellers for studies, was due to their recognition in the global stage eg: Jeweller World Dubai Awards. The generational business has been able to present several marketing successes to deal with the market requirements. The research methodology involves a qualitative approach. The board members of Vogue Jewellery were interviewed. Founders, marketing director, showroom staff were interviewed. A store walk through was also carried out by the group. The group of researchers involved four participants who visited the store and carried out the interviews. Researchers were part of a doctoral study group, the research being part of the outcomes of the study report.

4. DISCUSSION

The approach of Vogue Sri Lanka (2023) could be identified to be dedicated towards implementing a product oriented strategy. The organisation is giving each of its customers a certificate marking the quality of the product.

Workshop that drives craftsmanship and a cornerstone on implementing design

The above image illustrates the classic workmanship, working staff members and capital investment that has been made on the product design, manufacturing.

Tusker jewellery good ones

This was one of the innovation driven products - where the product can be separated down to four other products. Gold is a valuable investment. The product innovation has helped the business to achieve immense growth. Often setting up a LKR 1.1 Mn investment - which is both an investment and is wearable. The investment oriented wearable product has enabled for growth accounting for close to 40% of the sales.

Historical pictures

The images above illustrate the different historical images identifying the building and aspects of the business for the ability to set out one of the first jewellery mainstream retailers to enter the Colpetty market place. Colpetty in the 1960s was not a commercial business area, instead of Pettah being a core area. Often ridiculed for the decision to set up Headquarters in Colombo 03 - the organisation has transformed and is proof of correct decisions made.

Event pictures

Colombo Fashion Week is a consistent platform to display the Vogue collection. The visibility of the brand has been further enhanced with the right mix of events.

Celebrities association with the brand

Use of Sonu Nigam for product events. Similarly, leading actresses and actors have been recruited to carry the brand. Nevertheless, the design's uniqueness has attracted as long term clients.

Innovation mindset of the family members, and the encouragement of staff members to submit their designs.

Sri Lankan traditional designs are unique and provide a specific design to use.

Digital media use

Vogue Jewellers (pvt) Ltd

●●●●● 970 Reviews | #1 of 231 Shopping in Colombo | Shopping, Gift & Specialty Shops
 📍 528 Galle Rd., Colombo 00300, Sri Lanka | 🕒 Open today: 10:00 AM - 6:00 PM

Vogue focuses on getting a five (5) star rating on trip advisors. Enabling tourist income from jewellery shopping.

Taking risks has been part of the Family’s ability to cope with marketing pressures. Colombo 03 was a residential area, when Vogue made its first attempt to set up the store in a residential area. Several people have attempted to discourage the effort citing the poor business potential that could cause harm to the investment. However, the decision paid off, as Colombo 03 got transformed to be a commercial capital of Colombo.

Market is changing to imitation jewellery, changing the mindset with product innovation, and product value marketing.

Market is shifting towards imitation jewellery rather than the use of gold jewellery. Often Sri Lankan communities invested in Gold as a medium of investment. However, the changing taste and trends towards Bollywood films - K Films have influenced the jewellery choices. The Innovative mindset of the family and the team members have applied the advantages of the organisation.

CRM with a personal touch

CRM with a personal touch which is able to provide with the unique advantage for the process of enabling for the competitive advantage. Customer relationship is enabling for the different requirements that are established for efficiency in data collection and analysis. CRM is useful for the different aspects of maintaining customer closeness and also enabling a positive attunement in syncing with the customers more. In launch events, the loyal customers are often introduced.

5. CONCLUSION

In this research it is identifiable the following range of factors that have contributed to the successful operation of Vogue's marketing.

- (1) Visionary leadership of the family in ensuring that quality is drafted over short term gains

The generational leadership and grooming of leadership from within the family is an essential element which is to be recognised. In order to provide for the different requirements that are set out with. The leadership ability to provide continuous growth and a commitment for the team to grow. Similarly, the non-family members to further participate in the growth of the business is an essential element to consider. Non-family members are also recognised for their product innovations, service and business acumen with promotions. In order to provide the ability for the non-family members to climb the corporate ladder.

- (2) Marketing and product building strategy follows the vision and passion of the founders, family and organisation.

The uniqueness of tusker product range and the ability to involve reputed actors and actresses from Bollywood and locally to drive attention to their brand is both unique and drives results for the business.

Passion of the founders and family members - in a family membership based business could be identified as a core function which has been noted in the literature review as well. In recognising the passion involved in driving the business process.

- (3) Value marketing needs to be associated with logic and be able to show returns to customers.

Value of marketing needs to be assessed with logic and investment returns. This is a value that is to be derived for the business and enables the business to achieve much needed scale for the business to derive a process of attention and acceptance.

- (4) The success of the tusker version and the product categorisation will give results and show innovation capability.

Innovation capability by providing product category tuskers which are able to innovate. Results drive for the approach for the progress and categorisation of the capability. Innovation mindset and the need to promote innovation is well understood. An open door policy in recognising innovation is set out. The new innovation which is able to provide for the abilities to meet processes.

The above analysis does provide a greater range of insights which are able to pinpoint on the key competencies that are required for jewellery manufacturers. Similarly, the brand creation process of a successful jewellery manufacturer is established.

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